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Dynamic Analysis and Simulation of Transient Response in a Separately Excited DC Motor Using MATLAB/Simulink

BIIRAGBARA Peace Barididum & EKERIANCE Dominic Evanson

**Department of Electrical Engineering,
Faculty of Engineering,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study presented a comprehensive dynamic analysis and simulation of the transient response characteristics of a separately excited DC motor under varying operating conditions. A mathematical model of the motor was developed and simulated using MATLAB/Simulink to investigate key performance parameters including armature current, rotor speed, electromagnetic torque, back EMF, and terminal voltage during transient disturbances such as step changes in load torque. The results reveal that the motor exhibits typical first-order system behaviour, with transient performance significantly influenced by armature inductance and rotor inertia. The simulation confirms that sudden load applications lead to temporary deviations in speed and current, which stabilize after short durations. These insights are critical for the design of efficient control strategies in DC motor applications. The study underscores the importance of incorporating adaptive feedback control mechanisms to improve motor stability and response time under dynamic load conditions.

Keywords: Separately Excited DC Motor, Transient Response, MATLAB/Simulink, Armature Current, Electromagnetic Torque, Dynamic Simulation, Feedback Control.

INTRODUCTION

DC motors are widely used in domestic, commercial and various industrial applications [1]. They have played a pivotal role in electrical engineering applications such as electric drives, automation and transportation systems. Despite the growing use of AC machines and power electronics, DC motor still remains relevant because it is characterized by its simplicity, low power and variable speed applications, which has always made it very attractive. DC motor is a type of electrical machine that consumes DC electrical power to produce mechanical torque which could be rotational or translational in nature [2]. They are known as electromechanical energy converters.

DC motors are broadly classified in respect to the connection of the field winding (which is fixed) and the armature winding (which is rotating).

The difference between the self-excited DC motor and separately excited DC motor is that in the former, the field windings are connected across the terminal of the main voltage source while, in the latter, the armature and field windings are electrically separate from each other with the field winding excited by a separate DC source. Self-excited DC motors are categorized into shunt and series motors. For that of shunt motors, the field winding is linked in parallel with the armature winding with the armature and field voltage being the same while in DC series motors, the field winding is in series with the armature winding with the field winding carrying the same current as the armature winding. In compound DC motor, both series and shunt field windings are applied [3]. DC motor is said to be a cumulative compound motor if

the magnetic flux produced by series and shunt windings are in similar direction. Conversely, the DC motor is said to be a differential compound motor if the fluxes from the series and shunt fields are in opposite direction.

The transient response of DC motors is a critical aspect of their operational performance [4]. When subjected to sudden changes in voltage or mechanical load. These dynamic conditions occur during start-up, sudden load changes, or fault conditions, the machine's parameters such as current, speed, and torque respond dynamically before settling to steady-state values, therefore understanding these responses is essential for design, control of the motor driven systems, and protection of the electrical motors. The aim of this study is to utilize the knowledge of circuit analysis to model out a separately excited DC motor in order to experience the actual transient response of separately excited DC motor when subject to dynamic conditions. This study aims to model and simulate the transient behavior of a separately excited DC motor using MATLAB/Simulink. The specific objectives are to analyze how dynamic parameters such as load torque and armature voltage influence the armature current, electromagnetic torque, rotor speed, and back EMF during transient events. The study contributes by offering a validated simulation model that supports adaptive motor control system design

Transient conditions, such as sudden application of load, drop in voltage, and starting or braking can cause significant deviations in the performance of a DC motor. Without proper understanding and mitigation approach, the events can result to instability, overheating, mechanical stress, and system failure. Therefore, proper analysis and evaluation of DC motor behaviour under dynamic operating conditions is essential for optimum performance

LITERATURE REVIEW

DC Machines

DC machines are one of the most commonly used machines for electromechanical energy conversion before the invention of AC machines [5]. Converters which are used continuously to convert electrical input to mechanical output or vice versa are called electric machines. An electric machine is therefore a link between an electrical system and a mechanical system. In these machines, the conversion is reversible. If the conversion is from mechanical to electrical, the machine is said to act as a generator. If the conversion is from electrical to mechanical, the machine is said to act as a motor [6]. Therefore, the same electric machine can be made to operate as a generator as well as a motor. Figure 1 is diagram illustrating the electromechanical energy conversion in DC machine

Figure 1: Electromechanical Energy Conversion [7]

Electric motors exist to convert electrical energy into mechanical energy. This is done by two interacting magnetic fields; one stationary, and another attached to a part that can move. DC motors have the potential for very high torque capabilities (although this is generally a function of the physical size of the motor), are easy to miniaturize, and can be "throttled" via adjusting their supply voltage. DC motors are not just the simplest form of motors, but the oldest electric motors [8]. DC machines can also be used as brakes. The brake mode is a generator action but with the electrical power either regenerated or dissipated within the machine system, thus developing a mechanical braking effect. It also converts some electrical

or mechanical energy to heat, but this is undesired. The major parts of a DC machine are the stationary component, the stator, and the rotor, which is the rotating component. The major advantages of DC machines are easy speed and torque regulation [9].

Principle of DC Motor Operation

The basic principle of operation of an electric DC motor is based on simple electromagnetism [9]. A current carrying conductor generates a magnetic field which when placed in an external magnetic field, it will experience a force proportional to the current in the conductor and to the strength of the external magnetic field. The internal configuration of a DC motor is designed to harness the magnetic interaction between a current-carrying conductor and an external magnetic field to generate rotational motion. Therefore, the geometry of the brushes, commutator contacts, and rotor windings are designed such that when power is applied, the polarities of the energized winding and the stator magnet(s) are misaligned, and the rotor will rotate until it is almost aligned with the stator's field magnets [10]. As the rotor reaches alignment, the brushes move to the next commutator contacts, and energize the next winding. Figure 2 depicts the diagram illustrating the concept of DC motor operation.

Figure 2: Concept of a DC Motor Operation Diagram (11)

In the study carried out by [7], the evaluation of the transient response of a DC motor was analyzed and it was opined that by varying certain parameters of the DC motor system, the output waveform of the simulation would change respectively, and the simulation and modeling of the DC motor also gave an insight on the estimated output when testing the definite DC motor and the results from the simulation were never likely to occur in real time conditions due to the response times and condition of the actual motor.

Similarly, in the research work by [12], an appraisal of the transient response of a DC motor under no-loading and full-loading conditions was analyzed in using MATLAB/Simulink. It was concluded that simulation can be a very helpful tool in studying the dynamic behavior of D.C shunt motor and its interaction, with reading experiment. It was also shown that the simulation model correctly predicts the effect of the field resistance on the torque-speed characteristic of the D.C shunt motor.

Transients Response in a DC Machines

Several studies have analyzed the transient behaviour of DC machines, and of the opinion that transient response analysis is essential; for designing robust control system. Transient response is influenced by machine parameters such as armature resistance, inductance, inertia, and damping [13]. Advanced control techniques including PID, fuzzy logic and neural networks, have been applied to improve DC machine transient behaviour, but a fundamental understanding of the machine's natural response remains essential. There are basically three types of transients in a DC motors namely; Electrical transients, mechanical transients and electromechanical transients.

Electrical transients: These occur due to sudden changes in applied voltage or current.

Mechanical transients: These type happened due to changes in load torque or inertial effects.

Electromechanical transients: These occur as a result of coupling between electrical and mechanical behaviours [14]. While previous studies have employed MATLAB/Simulink for modeling DC motors, many focused either on steady-state behavior or lacked validation of transient conditions under real-world load disturbances. This study addresses this gap by incorporating both electrical and mechanical transients and evaluating their interactions, offering a more holistic insight for motor control system design.

METHODOLOGY

Modelling of Separately Excited DC Motor

In order to carryout out simulation of a system, the first is to establish is a suitable model. In this study, the system contains a separately excited DC motor. Therefore, a model based on the motor specifications needs to be obtained. The equivalent circuit diagram of the motor is as shown in Figure 3. The block diagram of the DC motor was modelled and simulated using MATLAB/ Simulink program. MATLAB/Simulink was selected due to its robust capabilities in simulating dynamic systems and ease of modeling transfer functions and control loops.

Figure 3: Schematic Diagram of a Separately Excited DC Motor [15]

A separately excited DC motor is modeled in MATLAB/Simulink. The system is subjected to a step change in load torque. The transient behavior of armature current, speed, and electromagnetic torque are analyzed using numerical simulation. In order to achieve the aim set out, the actions taken includes the following: The modeling process followed a structured approach: the motor's electrical equivalent circuit was first established and converted into system equations. Transfer functions were derived and transformed into block diagram models, implemented using MATLAB/Simulink. Simulation parameters were selected based on standard motor ratings, and a step change in load torque was applied to evaluate transient behaviours.

Assumptions Made

In this study the following assumption are made:

Separately excited DC motor is chosen

The armature is controlled

Field flux is constant

Load disturbance or step input is applied

System Characteristics Mathematical Modelling

The torque T is related to the armature current I_a by a torque constant K_m i.e.

$$T = K_m I_a \tag{1}$$

The back EMF E_a (generated voltage) is related to the angular speed W_m by the flux linkage constant K_m

$$E_a = K_m W_m \tag{2}$$

For separately excited DC motor, $K_m = E_a / W_m$

Applying Kirchhoff's Voltage Law in Figure 3;

$$V_t = E_a + I_a R_a + L_a dI_a / dt \tag{3}$$

$$V_f = R_f I_f + L_f dI_f / dt \tag{4}$$

Where;

V_f : Field voltage

R_f : Field resistance

I_f : Field current

L_f : Field inductance

From equation (2), armature circuit equation is deduced as shown in equation (5);

$$V_t = K_m W_m + I_a R_a + L_a dI_a / dt \tag{5}$$

Where:

V_t : Input or terminal voltage

R_a : Armature resistance

L_a : Armature inductance

The dynamic equation for the mechanical system is;

$$T = K_m I_a = J \frac{dW_m}{dt} + B W_m + T_L \quad (6)$$

Where:

T: Electromagnetic torque (Nm)

J: Inertial (Kgm^2)

B: Damping co-efficient

W_m : Angular speed(rad/sec)

T_L : Load torque

Modelling the Block Diagram

Applying Laplace transforms in equations (4), (5) and (6):

$$V_f(s) = R_f I_f(s) + L_f s I_f(s) \quad (7)$$

$$V_t(s) = K_m W_m(s) + R_a I_a(s) + L_a s I_a(s) \quad (8)$$

Substitute $\tau_a : L_a/R_a$, which is the electrical time constant of the armature

$$V_t(s) = K_m W_m(s) + R_a I_a(s) / (1 + s\tau_a) \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) is known as the electrical transfer function.

Similarly, from equation (6):

$$T(s) = K_m I_a(s) = J s W_m(s) + B W_m(s) + T_L(s) \quad (10)$$

$$W_m(s) = \frac{T(s) - T_L(s)}{B(1 + sJ/B)} \quad (11)$$

$$W_m(s) = \frac{T(s) - T_L(s)}{B(1 + s\tau_m)} \quad (12)$$

Where $\tau_m : J/B$ is the mechanical time constant of the system

Deducing from equations (8) and (2);

$$I_a(s) = \frac{V_t(s) - k_m W_m(s)}{R_a(1 + s\tau_a)} \quad (13)$$

$$I_a(s) = \frac{V_t(s) - E_a(s)}{R_a(1 + s\tau_a)} \quad (14)$$

From (12) and (14), the model block diagram can be created as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Block Diagram Representation of a Separately Excited DC Motor

Data setup and Creating the M-file on Simulink for Simulation

DC Motor Data Setup

Rated Voltage: 220 V

Armature Resistance (R_a): 1.5 Ω

Armature Inductance (L_a): 0.5 H

Load Torque (TL): Step variation from 0 to 5 Nm

Simulation Duration: 0 to 2 seconds

N: 1500rpm

$I_f = 0.75A$

$I_a = 15.4A$

$V_t = 220V$

$V_f = 220V$

$K_m = 1.4Nm/A$

$B = 0.018$

$J = 0.117Kgm^2$

Tool Used: MATLAB/Simulink

With the required specifications as shown above, a model of the DC motor was developed using Simulink. The input armature voltage (V_t) is summed with the internal EMF (E_a) and the result passed through the transfer function of the electrical characteristic to produce the armature current (I_a). This is fed to the torque constant to generate the torque which is fed to the transfer function of the mechanical system to generate the motor speed (W_m).

I. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The result from the simulated output for the armature current, rotor speed, torque, back EMF and voltage response for transient conditions of the DC motor model in Simulink is as shown in Figures 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 respectively.

• Discussion of Armature Current Response

As shown in Figure 5, when load is suddenly applied at $t = 0.5s$, the armature current spikes to meet the additional torque demand. The current stabilizes after the transient period ($\sim 0.8s$). The behaviour of DC motor shows constant armature current at steady state, but during transients there was sharp rise and then, the armature current settles. This behavior indicates the impact of inductance in slowing current response.

Figure 5: Plot of Armature Current Response Versus Time

Figure 5 illustrates the armature current response to a step load applied at $t = 0.5s$. The initial current spike reflects the motor's demand to overcome increased torque, followed by a gradual stabilization due to inductive damping. This behavior confirms the significance of armature inductance in transient scenarios.

Discussion of Rotor Speed Response

As shown in Figure 6, initially, the motor accelerates and stabilizes at no-load speed. When load torque is applied at time, $t = 0.5s$, it is observed that the speed drops temporarily and then stabilizes at a lower value. This behaviour indicates that at steady state, the motor speed is constant, but dip with application of load, then stabilizes. The transient dip is due to the mismatch between electromagnetic torque and load torque during the disturbance.

Figure 6: Plot of Speed Response Versus Time

Discussion of Electromagnetic Torque Response

As shown in Figure 7, it is noticed that electromagnetic torque increases immediately as load is applied. Overshoot occurs due to stored energy in motor inertia. Eventually, torque matches the load torque to maintain constant speed. It is observed that at transient state the load matches the load torque, but at transient, it overshoot, then matches the load at 2Nm

Figure 7: Plot of Electromagnetic Response Versus Time

Discussion of Back EMF Response

As seen in Figure 8, Back EMF is proportional to speed; it increases as speed increases. When speed drops after load application, the back EMF also reduces momentarily. Back EMF reflects how voltage balances the resistive and inductive drops in the armature circuit. It is observed that at steady state, Back EMF is constant, while it fluctuates as speed varies.

Figure 8: Plot of Back EMF Response Versus Time

Discussion of Voltage Response

As shown in Figure 9, supply voltage is assumed constant at 220 V. Small dips in internal voltage occur due to inductive transients. It is observed that at steady state, supply voltage is constant, while it fluctuates as speed varies.

Figure 9: Plot of Voltage Response Versus Time

CONCLUSION

The transient response of a DC motor under dynamic operating conditions involves coupled electrical and mechanical phenomena. The system's inductance, inertia, and load characteristics determine the nature of these transients. Accurate modeling and simulation are essential for designing stable and responsive motor control systems. This study carried out analysis of the transient response of a separately excited DC motor using mathematical modelling, and simulation using MATLAB/Simulink. The dynamic performance was evaluated under various operating disturbances.

The exact result (especially of the transient conditions) for the armature current, rotor speed, torque, back EMF and voltage were obtained. From the result of graphs obtained, it is observed that DC motor are inherently stable under normal transient conditions, and inertia as well as inductance greatly influence response time. Therefore, in order to enhance stability and performance of a DC motor, the motor should started by external starter, with application adaptive control strategy. The findings have practical implications for DC motor applications in electric vehicles, industrial automation, and robotics where quick adaptation to load changes is critical. Future work could explore the integration of adaptive control strategies such as fuzzy logic or PID tuning for improved transient response in real-time scenarios.

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